

DETERMINATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NEW MICROBIOLOGICAL PREPARATIONS IN THE FIGHT AGAINST GRAIN APHIDS AND SLIMY WORMS, THE MAIN PESTS OF GRAIN CROPS

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Abstract. *Since wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is one of the main products consumed by the population, it is necessary to carry out measures to control pests in a timely manner in order to obtain a high yield. The use of microbiological protective means in the fight against pests is of great importance for the protection of the environment and the cultivation of organic agricultural products. As a result of the conducted research, Bioturin and Ekobak bioinsecticide drugs showed high insecticidal activity against grain aphids and grain leaf beetle larvae.*

Keywords: *wheat, pest, larva, biological efficiency, *Bacillus thuringiensis*, bacteria.*

Introduction. Population growth is increasing as the world develops, and by 2021 the number of people is predicted to be 11.2 billion. The demand for grain products and other food products is increasing every year [1]. If the population growth rate increases, serious problems will arise in the future [2;3].

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is one of the oldest field crops, and it is the first cereal crop due to the fact that it is an excellent food for humans and it provides 40% of energy calories and 20% of protein [4; 5]. Therefore, it is considered one of the main crops and satisfies 35% of people's demand for food [6].

In such a case, yield reduction due to insects and pest attack may lead to food shortage problem in the future [7]. A sustainable approach consists of minimizing the risk of food shortages and harvesting in an environmentally friendly way to increase yields [8].

We turn to the biological method to grow a clean product in an ecological way. Recently, the *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) bacterium is of great importance for biological control. This bacterium is gram-positive, known for its spore-forming ability to produce crystalline proteins (Cry). Cry protein is toxic to many insects and therefore Bt is used as a microbial insecticide to improve resistance in plants through genetic modification [9].

When the insect larvae ingest the protein crystal, digestive enzymes present in the gut activate the toxin and cause a hole in the cell membrane of the gut, leading to paralysis of the gut and eventual death of the larvae [10].

The use of Bt as a biopesticide is as effective as chemical pesticides, so we can say that it is part of a holistic pest control strategy that creates resistance to chemical pesticides to control pests [11].

Biological pesticides are an environmentally friendly approach to control and minimize wheat pests while maintaining a diversity of beneficial insects [12].

Bioturin, based on *Bacillus thuringiensis* 26/1 strain, and Ecobak, based on *Bac.thuringiensis* 94 strain, were tested to determine their insecticidal activity against grain aphids and grain leaf beetles in wheat.

Research materials and methods

In order to determine the insecticidal activity of microbiological preparations in the fight against the main pests of wheat, in 2024, we conducted experiments on 2.3 hectares of the 7.3-hectare area of the farm "Otoboyev's dream" in Furqat district of Fergana region.

Polyakov et al., (1984); Osmolovsky G.E., Bondarenko N.V., (1978), carried out according to methods [13;14;15].

The number of mealybug larvae and grain aphids was counted during the period when the spiked cereal crops started the tuber and earing phase. The scale of logarithms was used to determine the number of pests per bush and the population density in a wheat field [16].

Determining the degree of damage to the leaves of grain crops was done using the 0-5 scale of Stamenkov, S. and Pankov, L. (1991) and the methods of Rouag N et al., (2012) [17].

Determining the insecticidal activity of biopreparations in field conditions was carried out using Khojayev's (2004) methodological guide [18].

Experiments: 1. Experimental option - Bioturin, - 2.0-3.0 l/ha

2. Experimental option - Ecobak, 3.0- l/ha

3. Sample option - Atila super 10% em.k. - 0.07 l/ha

4. The control option (untreated), and each option based on the scheme, was carried out in 3 repetitions.

These biopreparations were used against wheat aphids and grain aphids, and control work was carried out to determine the effectiveness of the preparations. After the drug was sprayed, we conducted calculations on the 3rd, 7th and 14th days. In the experiment, it was carried out with the help of an electronic hand sprayer at the expense of 300 liters of working liquid per hectare.

Research results and their discussion

In biological pest control, 90% of the world market consists of biopreparations made on the basis of *Bacillus thuringiensis* bacteria. Therefore, we conducted experiments to determine the insecticidal activity of microbiological preparations against the main pests of wheat (see Fig. A, B, C and D).

In the experiment Bioturin biopreparation 2.0-3.0 l/ha, Atila super, 10% em.k. - 0.07 l/ha consumption was tested 30-55 days before harvesting, after the flowering phase of wheat. According to the results of the experiment, the Bioturin biopreparation, processed at a rate of 2.0 liters, was 27.1% effective on the 3rd day, 48.7% on the 7th day, and 73.1% on the 14th day. biological efficiency, 31.8% on the 3rd day, 52.6% on the 7th day, and 83.0% biological efficiency on the 14th day when used at a rate of 3.0 liters. When Ekobak was applied at the rate of 3.0 liters per hectare, the efficiency was 33.4% on the 3rd day, 54.1% on the 7th day, and 84.1% on the 14th day. Atila super 10% em.k., taken as a model. when the chemical preparation was used at the

consumption rate of 0.07 liters per hectare, it was 52.3% effective on the 3rd day, 75.8% on the 7th day, and 88.7% biological efficiency was noted by the 14th day (Table 1).

Bioturin biopreparation against the larvae of the slime worm pest of grain when treated at a consumption rate of 2.0 liters showed a biological efficiency of 23.8% on the 3rd day, 40.4% on the 7th day, and 73.2% on the 14th day. 29.3% on the 3rd day, 54.4% on the 7th day, and 79.6% on the 14th day were recorded when used at a consumption rate of 0 liters.

When Ekobak drug was used at the rate of 3.0 liters per hectare, the efficiency was 32.2% on the 3rd day, 53.5% on the 7th day, and 82.4% on the 14th day.

Atilla super 10% em.k., taken as a model. chemical preparation was 47.7% effective on the 3rd day, 72.8% on the 7th day, and the highest biological efficiency was 86.0% by the 14th day (Table 2).

Conclusion: Based on the results obtained in our field experiments, Bioturin, a new biopreparation, at the rate of consumption of 2.0 and 3.0 liters, showed a high result against grain aphids on the 14th day of the calculation, which was 73.1-83.0%, while slime biological efficiency against worm larvae was 73.2-79.6%.

Ekobak preparation showed 84.1% biological efficiency against grain aphids and 82.4% against slimy worm larvae on the 14th day at the rate of 3.0 liters. Biopreparations prepared on the

basis of these entomopathogenic bacterial strains showed high bioinsecticide when used against pests of grain crops.

REFERENCES

1. Worldbank data (2022). Population growth (annual %). https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.GROW?end=2022&name_desc=false&start=1961&view=chart.
2. Dixon J, Braun H-J, Kosina P, Crouch J (2009). Wheat Facts and Futures 2009. Mexico, D.F.: CIMMYT. pp 1-95.
3. Pardey PG (2011). A strategic look at global wheat production, productivity and R & D developments. Czech J. Genet. Plant Breed. 47 (Special Issue): S6-S19.
4. Kumar P, Sarangi A, Singh DK, Parihar SS, Sahoo RN (2015) Simulation of salt dynamics in the root zone and yield of wheat crop under irrigated saline regimes using SWAP model. Agric Water Manag 148:72–83
5. Kundu PK, Acharjee TK, Mojid MA. Growth and yield of wheat under irrigation by sugar mills wastewater. Progress Agric. 2006; 24(1-2):211-218.
6. Miedaner T, Akel W, Flath K, Jacobi A, Taylor M, Longin F, Würschum T (2020) Molecular tracking of multiple disease resistance in a winter wheat diversity panel. Theoretical and Applied Genetics 133(2):419–431.
7. Johnson SN, Züst T (2018) Climate change and insect pests: resistance is not futile. Trends in Plant Sci 23(5):367–369.
8. Senapati N, Semenov MA (2020) Large genetic yield potential and genetic yield gap estimated for wheat in Europe. Glob Food Sec 24:100340.
9. Salehi Jouzani G, Seifinejad A, Saeedizadeh A, Nazarian A, Yousefloo M, Soheilvand S, Mousivand M, Jahangiri R, Yazdani M, Amiri RM (2008) Molecular evaluation of their toxicity on free-living and plant-parasitic nematodes. Can J Microbiol 54(10):812–822.
10. Vachon V, Laprade R, Schwartz J-L (2012) Current models of the mode of action of *Bacillus thuringiensis* insecticidal crystal proteins: a critical review. J Invertebr Pathol 111(1):1–12.
11. Matyjaszczyk E (2018) “Biorationals” in integrated pest management strategies. J Plant Dis Prot 125:523–527.
12. Sharma KR, Raju SVS, Jaiswal DK, Thakur S (2018) Bio pesticides: An effective tool for insect pest management and current scenario in India. Ind J Agric Allied Sci 4(2):59–62.
13. Polyakov I. Ya., Persov M. P., Smirnov V. A. Forecast of development of pests and diseases of agricultural crops (with a workshop): textbook for higher agricultural educational institutions in the specialty «Plant protection». L.: Kolos, 1984. 318 p.
14. Osmolovsky G.E., Bondarenko N.V. Entomology. 2nd ed., reprint. and additional. L.: Kolos: Leningrad department, 1980. 359 p.
15. Bondarenko N.V. “Biological plant protection.” Kolos 1978 -P.176-178.
16. Lowe H. The assessment of populations of the aphid *Sitobion avenae* in field trials// J. agr. Sc. – 1984. - № 2. – P.487-497.
17. Stamenkov, S. & Pankovi, L. 1991. Evaluating of wheat and barley resistance to the cereal leaf beetle (*Lema melanopus* L.). Zbornik radova Instituta za ratarstvo i povrtarstvo, Novi Sad, 19:247-251.
18. Khojayev Sh.T. Methodological guidelines for testing insecticides, acaricides and biologically active substances and fungicides// Tashkent.-2004. -B.37.